

Description of the predictability assessment methodology Deliverable D3.2

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Executive Summary

This report describes the methodology that will be used to produce information about wind predictability in the European wind atlas. A review of the state-of-the-art in predictability assessment is reported at different scales, from day ahead (short-term) to sub-seasonal (medium-term predictability), seasonal and decadal (long-term predictability). The report provides an overview of the potential applications of wind predictability, the sources of predictability, the available prediction systems and the methods to evaluate them.

Short-term predictability was first studied in the frame of the European project SAFEWIND. A summary of that work is included here in order to show the continuity of this activity in the NEWA project and how it will be integrated with other scales of prediction. Predictability mapping was carried out using forecasts from numerical weather prediction and comparing them with reanalysis data. Downscaling to site level to produce wind power predictability information, based on information from the planning phase, was also done in order to illustrate how a wind farm developer could anticipate costs of lack of predictability during the operational phase.

Medium to long term predictability is studied with global climate models. Preliminary assessment of predictability is also done using reanalysis data as a reference of the real state of the atmosphere. This allows to map predictability skill over Europe. Preliminary results detected at least two windows of opportunity (high forecast skill) over Europe, one at sub-seasonal time scale, for a lead time of 12-18 days, and another at seasonal scale, for a lead time of one month. This skill is found to exist mainly over Central and Northern Europe and to a lesser degree in the Iberian Peninsula during the winter months of December-February.

Having demonstrated that there is statistically significant wind speed skill during winter over some European areas, the end users could gain potential economic value using the forecasts instead of the climatology to base their decisions. Over these areas, novel techniques that employ this probabilistic information effectively to enhance the value of operational business decisions and quantitative risk management in the wind energy sector can be developed.

Further work will try to demonstrate the potential use of predictability with site observations. This will help potential users answer questions like: what can they expect on the use of wind forecast at different time horizons? How predictable the wind resource is at the site of interest? This information will be synthesized in the form of comprehensive maps of predictability skills over Europe so it can be used for spatial planning of wind energy development.

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Introduction

A wind atlas is useful for the planning phase of wind energy development, which can last several years: from strategic spatial planning, to site prospecting, to wind farm design and financing. Detailed and robust information about the characteristics of the wind resource across an area is crucial for the commercial evaluation of a wind farm.

The operational phase covers the lifetime of the wind farm which is typically assumed to extend for 20 years. Relevant variables in this phase are mainly the weather conditions and the wind farm power forecasts at different look-ahead times in connection to wind farm and transmission system operation and maintenance and energy trading. When these variables are characterized during the planning phase, in order to anticipate the associated operational costs, we talk about wind predictability assessment.

Together with the wind resource assessment information of the atlas it will be possible to improve spatial planning tools considering life-cycle cost models of wind farms. As a result financial risks will be also better evaluated throughout Europe.

By introducing wind power variability and predictability aspects in spatial planning tools, it is possible to obtain an integrated vision of the cost of wind energy throughout the deployment life cycle (IRENA, 2012). This enriched wind atlas allows a more comprehensive planning of wind energy deployment considering, as much as possible, all the stakeholders interests in a seamless modeling framework.

Short-term wind power predictability assessment was already analyzed at European scale in the FP7-Safewind project (Sanz Rodrigo et al., 2012). A subset of the results from that study is presented here in order to motivate a similar philosophy in NEWA to other prediction scales.

At time scales from one month to a decade into the future, current energy practices use an approach based on the future climate being a repetition of any retrospective climatology, but climate predictions have recently shown to provide additional value for energy applications (García-Morales and Dubois, 2007, De Felice et al., 2015).

Figure 1. Schematic illustrating progression from an initial value problem (daily weather forecasts) to a forced boundary condition problem (climate projections), with sub-seasonal, seasonal and decadal predictions in between (Adapted from Meehl et al., 2010).

Climate predictions cover the gap between weather forecasting and climate projections (Figure 1), and they can provide additional value for wind energy applications, especially in the management of power production plants (García-Bustamante et al., 2009; Lynch et al., 2014). In particular, the analysis of the main sources of skill in current climate prediction systems is relevant in a wind energy context to quantify offshore installation and operation and maintenance logistic costs.

CENER and BSC will bring together their experience on short-term (FP7-SAFEWIND) and seasonal-to-decadal (FP7-SPECS) predictability assessment to complement the probabilistic mesoscale model chain by producing information related with the sources of skill at different time horizons.

This deliverable has been divided as follows. In Section 1 an overview of the NEWA project and the goals of Wind Atlas are included. Subsequently, a classification of the main potential applications of the wind speed predictability assessment is explained in Section 2. Section 3 provides a description of the value of the predictability of wind speed at different timescales. A review of the state-of-the-art of the predictability in the prediction systems in all the considered time horizons is included in Section 4. The full description of the methodology, that is going to be applied in order to identify the main sources of predictability of wind speed, is in Section 5. In addition, some preliminary results have been showed in Section 6. Finally, the summary of the results gathered in this deliverable, the future plans and the usefulness of this contribution for the Wind Atlas are discussed in Section 7.

1. Wind Atlas Scope

The New European Wind Atlas will provide a unified high-resolution and freely available dataset of wind conditions in Europe. Wind statistics will cover onshore Europe and 100 km offshore plus the Baltic and the North Seas (Figure 2), with a horizontal resolution of 20-30 meters at least at 10 wind turbine relevant heights. The database will be based on at least 10 years of mesoscale simulations at 3 km resolution, with long-term corrections as well as subgrid microscale corrections to reduce the bias on the local mean wind resource.

In addition to wind resource information, the new wind atlas will provide information about site suitability conditions (turbulence intensity, wind shear, extreme wind speed), wind variability as well as wind power predictability from day-ahead to decadal. A probabilistic wind atlas methodology using mesoscale models is introduced in D3.1.

Besides variables of immediate use by resource planners, the wind atlas will provide means to feed boundary conditions on microscale models. This will allow not only to improve the wind atlas predictions at local level when better site data becomes available but also to allow a coherent integration with wind farm design tools. Hence, a generalized wind atlas, i.e. free of side effects, will be also part of the NEWA database. Downscaling methodologies with microscale models are introduced in D3.3.

Figure 2: Initial extension of the European domain for the New European Wind Atlas and location of high fidelity experiments

Integral to the wind atlas methodology is the assessment of the associated uncertainties. The ultimate goal of the wind atlas is to reduce the uncertainties on the assessment of wind resource and the wind conditions that affect the design of wind turbines. To this end, the model-chain will be thoroughly validated across Europe with dedicated experiments and historical wind resource assessment campaigns from industry. The model evaluation strategy is described in D3.4.

An uncertainty map will calculate the confidence of the wind atlas and, therefore, the intensity to which in situ measurement must be employed before development of a wind farm.

2. Forecasting for Wind Energy Applications

Managing the variability of wind generation is a key aspect for an optimal integration of wind power in the electrical grid, especially when large penetration is sought as it is the case for European targets of 20% share of renewables by 2020. According to the European Wind Energy Association (EWEA) wind energy is expected to contribute with 15.7 to 18.4% of EU's energy demand (EWEA, 2009) in 2020. Hence, accurate forecasts at different temporal scales are a key piece in the decision-making process because they can allow wind energy users take calculated and precautionary actions with potential costs savings.

Wind power forecasting is a matter of temporal scales as an inherent characteristic of the wind speed variability of the weather (Lange and Focken, 2005). The wind assessment model-chain framework with typical scale ranges for each sub-model level and associated applications and flow modeling approaches of various physical fidelity levels are shown in Figure 3 (Sanz Rodrigo et al., 2016).

Figure 3: Wind assessment modelling framework indicating typical model scale ranges, relevant outputs for different applications and high-level fidelity levels (the shading indicates the computational cost). (Sanz Rodrigo et al., 2016)

The use of wind power forecasting is normally associated to the operational phase of a wind farm in connection to different end users and prediction horizons (Wang et al., 2011). In the very short-term, from seconds to a few minutes to six hours, forecasts are useful to predict sudden events like ramps that can be managed by turbine and wind farm control (Mendes et al., 2013). In the range from six hours to 2-3 days, short-term forecasting is used by transmission system operators (TSO) for power system management (scheduling, reserves planning, congestion management, etc) (Giebel et al., 2011). Wind farm operators use day-ahead and intraday forecasts for trading in the energy market (Pinson et al., 2007). Medium-term forecasting up to a week-ahead is used for operation and maintenance planning of wind farms (Jacobsen and Rugbjerg, 2005), conventional power plants or transmission lines. Long-term weather forecasting beyond a week-ahead is particularly interesting to support offshore wind farms servicing logistics during the construction and operation phases (Scholz-Reiter et al., 2010). Finally, very long-term seasonal and decadal wind climate forecasting is relevant to understand and quantify wind resource, which is a key element to multiple user profiles in the wind energy sector both in pre and post-construction (Figure 4). For instance climate predictions at seasonal timescales can inform wind energy investors about the volatility of the future wind resource and how this risk can have an impact on the return of investment (Soret et al., 2015).

Figure 4: Classification of the decisions that can potentially benefit from climate predictions. This classification links the decisions associated to the operational phase of a wind farm with the most relevant prediction horizons.

From seasonal scales driven by global circulation weather patterns to daily cycles due to temperature changes and to sub-minute turbulence variations generated by local topography, wind power integration is a multi-scale problem. Within the energy industry there are multiple actors with specific requirements for climate information in different temporal scales. Manufacturers, project developers, project investors, consultants and energy trading companies are some of the types of users that already have shown their interest in sub-seasonal to decadal prediction because several potential applications of these predictions have been identified.

2.1 Potential applications of the Sub-seasonal predictions

In recent years there has been a growing interest in the scientific, operational and applications communities in developing sub-seasonal forecasts that fill the gap between medium-range weather forecasts (up to two weeks) and seasonal ones (3-6 months). Many management decisions fall into the sub-seasonal scale, thus the predictability at this timescale promises to be of great economic and societal value (Robertson et al., 2015).

Examples of sub-seasonal prediction applications can be found in many sectors: in agriculture, for instance, sub-seasonal forecasts can support operational decision making on the timing of cultivating, irrigating, spraying and harvesting. Viable forecast information beyond the traditional 10 day window can extend the time horizon for agricultural commodity price analysis and forecasting, and so support farmers' decisions about production, storage and marketing, as well as logistical decision in dealing with regional shortfalls and excess product availability (Curry, 2015).

Sub-seasonal forecasts can also improve the decision making of insurance companies, financial institutions (trading commodities that are impacted by weather), supermarket chains (as the sales volume of certain products is dependent upon temperature), health services and disaster mitigation and also in the energy sector (McGregor et al., 2006).

Sub-seasonal forecast applications of wind, solar and hydropower generation can help stabilize energy costs and supply by improving scheduling and trading, maintenance scheduling, reducing curtailments and imbalance penalties, improving decisions about reserve energy sources, maximizing grid integration, and planning capacity commitments. Specifics groups from the commercial sector that could benefit from sub-seasonal forecasts include energy trading firms, regional power generators/suppliers and investors (Curry 2015).

2.2 Potential applications of the Seasonal predictions

Over the past 30 years, the development of the predictions at seasonal timescales, which range from one month up to 7 months into the future, has grown from a research activity undertaken in a few academic and research institutes, to a routine operational activity in a number of meteorological forecast services (Weisheimer and Palmer 2014).

As a result, seasonal climate forecasts are increasingly being used across a range of application areas (Dessai and Bruno Soares, 2013). For example, information about seasonal average rainfall and temperature for the growing season can potentially influence a farmer's decision about which crops to plant ahead of time, or a humanitarian organization's strategy for anticipating food shortages in drought-prone regions of the developing world, but seasonal predictions can also provide robust information of the future variability in wind power resources.

The probabilistic seasonal predictions can be used as a tool to inform wind energy users with greater accuracy than current approaches at seasonal timescales (Torralba et al., 2016), because probabilistic seasonal climate predictions provide information about the uncertainty of these forecasts that allows their application in different decision-making processes.

Operations and Maintenance (O&M) teams of offshore wind farms need to schedule operations during the less windy periods in order to minimize the risk of storms and swell conditions. For grid operators, being aware in advance of the amount of renewable energy that will go into the grid can help schedule traditional power plant operations. For the financial teams running the wind farm business, having a budget of the energy they will produce in the coming months is of crucial importance to anticipate cash flow. In all of these cases the decision makers in each user profile use a retrospective climatology to have an estimation of the expected wind. Indeed, combining long-term reference datasets with on-site measurements by means of dynamical and statistical downscaling methodologies to forecast the future conditions has become quite standard in the wind industry (Landberg et al., 2003, Sanz Rodrigo et al., 2013).

2.3 Potential applications of the Decadal predictions

Decadal prediction is a relatively new field of research and focuses on time-evolving climate conditions up to the next 30 years. Skillful decadal predictions will prove invaluable to numerous aspects of society: climate-related health issues, such as the preparation for and possible prevention of the spread of viruses and diseases, planning for possible disasters from increased forest and bush fires, heat waves, droughts, floods and major storms including hurricanes; long-term resource management decisions in industries such as agriculture, forestry and fisheries; development of freshwater allocation strategies and infrastructure planning. Since monetary investments are considered at decadal time scales, financial institutions could use such climate predictions for planning investment strategies (Hurrell et al., 2010).

Decadal and multidecadal wind power variability has not been traditionally taken into account for the planning of wind power facilities and management, due to the unavailability of time series long enough to detect changes at those time scales. Wind industry uses average values to cover the information at decadal time scales for the development of wind atlases or wind resource availability analyses (Kirchner-Bossi et al., 2014). However, as the life span of a wind farm typically ranges between 20 and 25 years, inter-annual to decadal predictions could add extra information in the decision making processes related to the future planning (Reyers et al. 2015). For example, it could help explaining and reproducing the 13-year-long and 25-year-long cycles of the Spanish wind power generation detected by Kirchner-Bossi et al. (2014).

3. The value of Predictability in Spatial Planning

The spatio-temporal characteristics of wind predictability can be exploited to contribute to a more efficient and secure integration of wind energy in the power grid. Hence, smart consideration of meteorological aspects can not only promote optimum use of the wind energy potential but can also contribute to important savings in operational costs. For instance, at site level, it is possible that the market value of wind power of a certain wind farm decreases if day-ahead wind power predictions are very inaccurate although the wind resource is very good.

When aggregating forecasts at larger scales, temporal variability decreases and predictability increases due to spatial error compensations. With distance, wind speeds tend to be less correlated, and this results also in uncorrelated forecasting errors. The weaker these correlations are, the higher the error smoothing will be. Hence, the predictability of a region is always better than that of a single wind farm (Focken et al., 2002). This is known as the portfolio effect, because a wind power operator will find market benefits in distributing his wind farm portfolio along large areas whose wind patterns are maximally uncorrelated. This way, a compensation of forecasting errors takes place and leads to significant improvements in the aggregated predictability and market revenues. The portfolio effect is also beneficial for the TSOs in reducing the balancing costs associated with reserves and congestion management. This can be especially advantageous in the development of a European grid with a unified energy

market, where strong cross-border interconnections allow an efficient exchange of energy across the EU. Hence, higher penetration of renewable energy generation is possible, reducing energy supply risks and lowering the electricity prices (EWEA, 2009; Rombauts et al., 2011).

Despite being relevant to multiple roles in the wind energy sector, the primary potential user of climate predictions is the energy trading sector. Nowadays, practically no country can cover its energy needs from its own sources. This increases the significance of energy trading not only for supplying energy but also for buffering the risks of supply shortages or price fluctuations. Supply and demand are the determining factors for the market and important decisions must be made in order to attain adequate load balancing between production and consumption. Production and its costs are variable and depend on many factors, such as wind speed for wind energy, fuel prices for thermal energy and rainfall for hydro power. This scenario is further complicated by the variability of demand itself. Energy traders must make their choices based upon which course of action will be the optimal in terms of expected production from renewable sources, fuel prices, water shortages, energy prices, etc.

One of the difficulties trading analysts face when dealing with probabilistic climate predictions is conciliating an array of probabilities with a yes/no decision (Cloke and Pappenberger 2009). To overcome this situation, several methods exist to translate probabilities into monetary risk, which is the expected value of losses or profits. Flood risk management, for instance, is a field where probabilistic forecasting is gradually being adopted. Risk-based approaches calculate the expected monetary values and adequate thresholds are fixed accordingly. Thus a consistent decision-making policy can be defined (Dale et al, 2014). However, in order to promote the incorporation of probabilistic predictions in the decision-making process of climate analysts in energy trading firms the first step is to demonstrate the added value of these predictions compared to current practices.

The evaluation of the potential users that - for the regions where the prediction system is skillful- the hit rate of climate predictions can be greater than mere climatology and thus increase the perception of value for climate predictions promoting their inclusion in the decision making processes that require wind resources, is a challenge for the climate community.

To demonstrate the added value of the climate predictions, WP41 of the EUPORIAS project (<http://www.euporias.eu/>) addresses the value of climate information for decision making processes. D41.2 defines several methodologies for the "value" assessment for different sectors, and at BSC we are currently developing the case studies and prototypes related with the wind energy sector (Torralba et al., 2015)

4. Predictability Assessment at Different Scales

Climate predictability is the extent to which an informative prediction is possible if an optimum procedure is used (Doblas-Reyes et al., 2013). We shall use the term predictability assessment when we quantify wind predictability during the planning phase of a wind farm (Sanz Rodrigo et al., 2013). This can be associated to the

prediction of the hub-height wind speed (the meteorological wind resource), the gross power output for a specific turbine model or the net wind power output, which includes wind farm losses due to wake effects and other environmental aspects that are site and wind-farm layout specific.

Wind power predictability assessment is done using the same tools of the operational forecasting environment but applied, in hindcast mode, to virtual time series of wind power production that have been generated with resource assessment models. Similarly to wind resource assessment, the characterization of predictability depends on the resolution of the model used to generate the time series. Then, we can speak about regional or large-scale predictability in connection to reanalysis data, with several tens of kilometers of horizontal resolution, or local-scale predictability in connection to site measurements (Sanz Rodrigo et al, 2013).

Depending on the prediction horizon different models are used. This section describes the predictability of the models that will be used in NEWA and the different wind information that will be included in the New European Wind Atlas.

4.1 Short-Term (from hours to a few days) Predictability

Short-term predictability in the context of spatial planning was analyzed in the FP7-SAFEWIND European project (Sanz Rodrigo et al., 2012).

In the context of spatial planning and project financing, a wind atlas methodology should use a consistent modeling framework to deal with both hindcast and forecast simulations. The core model is a numerical weather prediction (NWP) model, driven by Global Circulation Models (GCM) outputs produced by met-offices like NCEP/NCAR in the United States or ECMWF in Europe. GCMs are used, with data assimilation systems, to resolve the large scale fields of the weather, at resolutions of several hundreds of kilometers, in order to define the state of the atmosphere at typically 6-hourly intervals (so called analyses in forecasting and reanalysis in hindcasting). NWPs operating at regional scale refine the weather patterns to produce forecasts at mesoscale level, at resolutions of few kilometers and an hourly output frequency (Hahmann et al, 2014). Even though there are mesoscale models that can proceed with physical downscaling to microscale levels, due to the computational cost, all the sub-grid scales are not resolved but rather parameterized, i.e. semi-empirical formulation is used to fill the sub-grid gap which is not simulated by the meteorological models. This will typically result in wind speed bias in complex terrain areas due to unresolved speed-ups generated by the sub-grid topography. Microscale models can be used to correct these biases and simulate wake effects from nearby wind turbines (Badger et al, 2013).

When dynamic data from the wind farm is available in almost-real time it can be used to build statistical models, so called Model Output Statistics (MOS), which act as a transfer function between the NWP outputs and the wind power predictions. These tools are more efficient than full-physical models and have proven very effective at removing systematic errors coming from both the NWP and the wind farm power curve. This is the standard approach for operational short-term deterministic wind power forecasting. Probabilistic forecasting constitutes an important field of research as it allows the

introduction of uncertainty in the prediction. An up-to-date review of wind power forecasting models can be found in Giebel et al. (2011) and Foley et al. (2012).

Improvements in day-ahead wind power forecasting were very significant in the first decade of 2000. Lange et al. (2006) report wind power forecasting errors, in terms of RMSE in % of installed capacity, in the E.ON Netz area of the German grid improving from 10% in 2001 to 6.5% in 2006. For Germany this error is of the order of 5% while for an individual wind farm in complex terrain the error can be as high as 20% (Giebel et al., 2011).

Short-term predictability mapping in Europe was first developed by ForWind at the University of Oldenburg (Sanz Rodrigo et al., 2012), by comparing forecasts up to 72 hr from COSMO-EU model with ERA Interim reanalysis on a grid with horizontal resolution of 4.1x7 km for the year 2010. Wind speed was converted to wind power, by using a reference power curve based on two 2-MW commercial wind turbines and assuming a homogeneous wind farm distribution at each grid point.

Forecast errors are calculated following Madsen et al. (2005). Figure 5 shows the mean absolute error (MAE) normalized by the load factor (mean wind power production), for one day and three days ahead. Not surprisingly, the forecast error is highly dependent on the local orography: the more complex the terrain is, the larger the forecast errors. However, not only the orography has an influence on the forecast error, but also some meteorological phenomena. For instance, in the Mediterranean, Mistral winds in Southern France are well predicted while cut-off lows (cool air pools) in the South of Italy are difficult to predict. Wind power forecast errors strongly depend on the load factor which itself depends on the topography. Especially areas of complex terrain have a faster forecast error development than e. g. the northern offshore regions.

Figure 5: MAE of the wind power forecast normalised with the load factor for 2010 for forecast day 1 (left) and day 3 (right). (Sanz Rodrigo et al., 2013).

Depending on the end-use it could be interesting to downscale predictability to site level, for example in connection to wind farm development, or to upscale to regional level, for example in connection to TSO management.

Upscaling takes advantage of smoothing effects that compensate errors from different sites within the area of influence of, for instance, a TSO zone (can take several hundreds of kilometers). Error compensation depends on how uncorrelated is the wind climate in the region. For example, using a 100 km radius to smooth predictability over each grid point, the error reduction can be up to 50% in some regions of complex terrain. Some coastal areas in Northern Germany also show similar reductions, despite the relatively low terrain complexity, due to error compensation between offshore and onshore winds.

Downscaling to site level is relevant for wind energy developers interested in calculating the cost of lack of predictability when they trade in the energy. Of course, the financial model depends on the energy market rules (Girard et al., 2013), that can be different depending on the country, and the strategy of the wind farm operator, that can participate in the market with a portfolio of wind farms to benefit from the error compensation explained before.

In order to incorporate site and wind farm array effects, a microscale wind farm flow model is used to generate virtual time series of wind energy production based on mast measurements from the resource assessment measurement campaign. This virtual time series is fed to a MOS statistical model to train an operational short-term wind power forecasting model as if they were actual production series. Running this model in hindcast mode, it is possible to generate a site-specific record of predictability information that can be used in combination to a market model to assess grid imbalance costs (Sanz Rodrigo et al., 2013).

Figure 6: Wind power forecasting error versus look-ahead time for two wind farms, one in complex terrain in the North of Spain (left) and another one in South in simple terrain (right). The predictability from the "real" operational production data is compared with the predictability from the "virtual" production data generated from the wind speed measurements during the planning and operational phases. (Sanz Rodrigo et al., 2013).

Figure shows the dependency of the forecasting errors with the look-ahead time for two wind farms in Spain: one in the North situated in complex terrain and one in the South situate in simple terrain. The errors from the real production data are compared with those obtained from the virtual production data from the planning and operational phases. Daily cycles of the errors are observed since the forecasting model is initialized once a day allowing for the highlighting of the intraday error variability of the global input data. These cycles are quite repeatable from year to year in the first wind farm as a result of the similitude of wind climate observed between the planning and operational

phases. This is not the case in second wind farm where a distinct daily pattern is observed in both phases. Despite of the larger wind climate variability observed in second wind farm, predictability is higher due to the much simpler local topography which results in higher performance of the mesoscale model. The error growth is also less pronounced in the second wind farm. Similarly to wind resource assessment, the impact of interannual variability on predictability needs to be determined in order to produce robust long-term estimates.

4.2 Sub-seasonal (from 2 weeks to 1 month) Predictability

4.2.1 General description of the Sub-seasonal forecasts

Sub-seasonal forecasting, otherwise known as dynamical monthly forecasting, fills the gap between medium-range weather forecasting and seasonal forecasting. At this time scale, the atmospheric system has lost most of its memory from the initial conditions; at the same time, this scale is too short for the influence of the ocean state to differ significantly from its initial state and thus to beat persistence forecasts (Vitart, 2013).

As a consequence, predicting hourly variations after 5-6 days (especially of wind speed, with its intermittent nature) is not easy. However, there is opportunity for skillful predictions over longer time-averaging windows, for example by taking a weekly time average; in this way, the unpredictable short-term fluctuations are reduced and predictive skill arises from the slow changes in the boundary forcing. Weekly averages of monthly forecasts of surface wind speed, temperature and geopotential height have already demonstrated to produce skillful forecasts (Lynch et al., 2014; Hudson et al., 2011).

Ten years ago, only a couple of operational meteorological services were producing sub-seasonal forecasts, but improvements of these forecast systems have slowly enhanced their skill, due to the increasing spatial resolution, the improved physical parametrizations (especially convection), better initial conditions and extended reforecast set. However, in recent years, many operational forecasting systems dedicated to sub-seasonal predictions have been implemented and now the majority of the Global Producing Centers (GPCs) have a forecasting system designed to target the sub-seasonal time range.

A new World Weather Research Programme/World Climate Research Programme (WWRP/WCRP) initiative on sub-seasonal to seasonal (S2S) prediction has recently been launched to foster collaboration and research in the weather and climate communities, with the goals of improving forecast skill and physical understanding, promoting forecast uptake by operational centers, and exploitation by the applications community (Robertson et al., 2015).

One of the main sub-seasonal prediction systems is the multi-member ensemble monthly forecast model (EFM) of the European Center for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF). In addition, other sub-seasonal prediction systems have also been developed by different institutions around the world such as: the Japan Meteorological Agency (JMA), National Center for Environmental Prediction (NCEP/NCAR), Météo-France (MF) and Beijing Climate Center (BCC).

4.2.2 Sub-seasonal sources of predictability

It is known that the main sources of predictability at this time range come from the Madden-Julian Oscillation or MJO (Vitart and Jung, 2010), the stratospheric-troposphere interactions (Baldwin and Dunkerton, 2001), the land/ice/snow initial conditions, the ENSO and NAO teleconnections, blocking conditions, local SST anomalies and soil moisture anomalies (Koster et al., 2010). However, while all these processes have the potential to act as climate drivers, only a few have been successfully reproduced until now. In particular, the representation of MJO in models has improved substantially in recent years and some models now have skill up to 20 days in advance (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Decrease of the magnitude (amplitude) of the error associated to the Madden-Julian Oscillation. Each year shows the mean error estimated using a more sophisticated version of the operational sub-seasonal forecasting system employed at the ECMWF. It is evident how after 2006, the magnitude decrease substantially (Vitart 2013).

4.3 Seasonal Predictability

4.3.1 General description of the seasonal forecasts

Seasonal prediction systems produce probabilistic forecasts up to six months ahead. The feasibility of seasonal prediction largely rests on the existence of slow, and predictable, variations in soil moisture, snow cover, sea-ice, and ocean surface temperature, and how the atmosphere interacts and is affected by these boundary conditions.

The predictions at seasonal timescales share with the numerical weather prediction the difficulty of initializing the simulations with a realistic state of the atmosphere and the need to periodically verify different aspects of their quality, while additionally are burdened by uncertainties in feedback processes that also play a central role in constraining climate projections. Seasonal predictions have to deal also with the challenge of initializing all the components of the climate system (ocean, sea ice, and land surface).

Statistical forecasts based on relationships between variability of seasonal mean climate and slowly-varying climate drivers such as the El Niño-Southern Oscillation (ENSO; e.g. Barnston, 1994 Drosdowsky and Chambers, 2001) have been used for several decades. However, in recent years a growing number of global dynamical climate models are used for seasonal forecasts (e.g. Alessandri et al., 2011; Cottrill et al., 2013).

The ECMWF has been at the forefront of seasonal predictions for many years. Research on predictability on seasonal timescale in the early 1990s led to the implementation of the first ECMWF seasonal forecast system based on a global ocean-atmosphere coupled model in 1997, and a successful forecast of the major 1997-1998 El Niño (Stockdale et al. 1998). All results presented in Section 6 at seasonal time scales are based on the (state-of-the-art) operational seasonal forecast System 4 from the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF), a seasonal prediction system which has been adopted as operational since November 2011 (Molteni et al., 2011).

4.3.2 Seasonal sources of predictability

The El Niño-Southern Oscillation (ENSO) is the most important source of predictability at seasonal timescales. The large spatial shifts in the tropical Pacific rainfall associated with ENSO lead to large-scale changes in global circulation and precipitation, which make ENSO a primary source of predictability in remote regions (Figure 8).

As in the tropical Pacific, modes of variability exist in the tropical Atlantic and Indian basins. For instance, the Atlantic Niño (Chang et al., 2006) seems to be strongly linked to ENSO and, hence, its predictability might be determined by the Pacific variability and, at the same time, affect the occurrence of ENSO events. The Indian Ocean Dipole (Saji et al., 1999) is also an important seasonal source of predictability since it could be predictable up to 6 months into the future.

Seasonal forecast systems showed only modest levels of skill in predicting surface winter climate around the Atlantic Basin and associated fluctuations in the North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO) at seasonal lead times, however a recent work (Scaife et al., 2015) has demonstrated that key aspects of European and North American winter climate and the surface NAO are highly predictable months ahead.

Relatively long-lived (up to 2 months) atmospheric anomalies can arise from stratospheric disturbances that can affect the troposphere by the quasi-biennial oscillation (Marshall and Scaife, 2009) and the sudden stratospheric warmings (Orsolini et al., 2011). In addition the accuracy of seasonal predictions can also be influenced by the land component of the climate system, which includes soil moisture and snow cover

extent and the long term changes in atmospheric composition such as increases in greenhouse gases and aerosol concentrations and land cover change, which are an important source of nonstationarity of the climate system (Doblas-Reyes et al., 2013).

Figure 8. Main sources of predictability of wind speed. Each color corresponds to a different timescale: sub-seasonal (blue), seasonal (red) or decadal (green). The acronyms employed are: NAO (North Atlantic Oscillation), ENSO (El Niño Southern Oscillation), MJO (Madden-Julien Oscillation), IPO (Inter-decadal Pacific Oscillation), AMO (Atlantic Meridional Oscillation), AN (Atlantic Niño), IOD(Indian Ocean Dipole), SCE (Snow Cover Extent).

4.4 Decadal Predictability

4.4.1 General description of the Decadal Predictions

Decadal predictions lie between seasonal forecasts and long-term climate change projections, and focus on time-evolving climate conditions over the next 1-30 years. Like seasonal predictions group data in monthly values to reduce the climatic noise, also decadal predictions usually group data, in monthly values or yearly values.

Since water has a much greater thermal capacity than the air, ocean variations evolve more slowly and live much longer than the weather in the atmosphere. For this reason, decadal forecasts are essentially predicting how the oceanic circulation will evolve over the next few years and its subsequent impact on the atmosphere.

Decadal forecasts take into account at the same time the evolution of both the intrinsic natural internal variability and the external forcing change from past emissions of anthropogenic greenhouse gas, aerosol loadings in the atmosphere, variations in solar irradiance and volcanic activity. Decadal predictions require initialization of coupled general circulation models with the best estimates of the current observed state of the atmosphere, oceans, cryosphere and land surface (Hurrell et al., 2010).

This timescale is characterized by a forced climate change signal that is often of a comparable magnitude of internally generated climate variations (Meehl et al., 2010). While long-term climate projections (30-100 years) are not synchronized with

observations because they have been started from randomly selected preindustrial states and seek to describe only climate trends, and not the details of individual days, seasons or years, decadal predictions were also developed to forecast the actual time-evolving climate, like seasonal predictions. Thus, they are also partly an 'initial value problem', because detailed knowledge of the best estimates of the current observed state of the atmosphere, oceans, cryosphere and land surface is needed (Figure 1).

One of the more widely-used decadal prediction system was developed in the framework of the CMIP5 (the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project phase 5), which is the suite of model experiments designed to advance climate science research and to inform the IPCC (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change) assessment process, use dynamical models of the coupled ocean-atmosphere-ice-land system, and possibly additional components of the Earth system (Taylor et al., 2012). CMIP5 consists mainly of 10-30-years integrations starting in 1960, 1980 and 2005 with a minimum of 3 members for model, for a total of more than 18 models. However, models with 6-hourly wind speed output are only 6 of them. They will be carefully explored to check their consistency and the most performant, higher resolution models will be adopted in this project to generate a probabilistic multi-model ensemble of decadal predictions.

4.4.2 Decadal sources of Predictability

A significant source of predictability at decadal timescale in the North Atlantic is related to the decadal variability in the heat and freshwater content of the Atlantic Ocean and the observed decadal changes in the ocean circulation. This variability is produced by the links between the Atlantic Multi-decadal Oscillation (AMO) and the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC) (Hurrell et al., 2010) that have produced changes in the Atlantic sea surface temperatures (SSTs) which affect regional climate trends over regions as North America and Europe (Einfield et al., 2001; Sutton and Hodson, 2005).

Across the whole Pacific basin, decadal fluctuations of the strength of the wintertime low pressure system co-vary with seas surface temperature in what has been termed the 'Inter-decadal Pacific Oscillation' (IPO, see also Figure 8). IPO influence climate across North and South America, Asia and Australia, and has also important ecological consequences, including major shifts in distribution and abundance of important commercial fish species (Hare et al., 2000).

Finally, another important climate driver at this timescale at mid latitudes is the Snow Cover Extent (SCE) in the Northern Hemisphere (García-Serrano, 2015).

5. Methodology to assess the Wind Predictability in Europe

In this section the methodology to perform the predictability assessment of the near surface wind speed at different timescales has been detailed. Some of the methodologies, whose preliminary results have been included in the Section 6, are explained in this section but also a description of the planned analyses, which are going to be implemented in the next months, has also been included.

The first step of the assessment is the same for each timescale, it consists on the comparison of the forecasts with the observations by means of different skill scores, each one developed to capture a particular aspect of the forecast system.

The second step is also common to the three timescales and it consists in the detection of the strength of the relationship between wind speed and its various sources of predictability (see Figure 8).

The rationale to employ the highest number of simulations possible is to reduce the wind speed inaccuracy and bias, since averaging across a number of simulations, model errors partially compensate each other. The use of multi-model ensembles also allows to quantify the uncertainty associated to the forecasted values of wind speed, by measuring the spread between the different simulations. An illustration of the value of multi-model forecasting has been explored for in the EUROSIP project (EUROSIP, 2015).

5.1 Data processing

5.1.1 Sub-seasonal predictions

To better understand the sub-seasonal methodology, we have prepared a preliminary study where we explore the predictability of different sub-seasonal systems, evaluating how the predictability evolves at different lead times. We have selected a case study to assess the performance of these predictions for a particular week in Europe, the first week of February (from 2nd to 8th) in 2015, when the sub-seasonal prediction systems were operational. This evaluation has been done to illustrate the evolution of the predictability at different lead-times and also to compare the forecast quality of different prediction systems.

The case study is based on three different sub-seasonal prediction systems from the archive produced by the European S2S project (<http://s2sprediction.net/>):

- **ECMWF** sub-seasonal prediction system is a global ensemble system that simulates initial uncertainties using singular vectors and ensemble of data assimilation and model uncertainties due to physical parameterizations using a stochastic scheme, based on 51 members, run twice a week (Monday and Thursday at 00Z) up to day 46.
- **CMA** prediction system has been developed by the Beijing Climate Center (BCC). It produces sub-seasonal forecasts every day since 1 Jan 1994 and end with a 60-day integration. Each forecast consists of 4 ensemble members, which are initialized at 00 UTC of the first forecast day and 18, 12 and 06 UTC of the previous day, respectively.
- **NCEP** real-time forecasts consist of a 16-member ensemble run every day. The S2S archive contains all the NCEP real-time forecasts since 1st January 2015, and the associated re-forecasts.

The predictions initialized the 15th, 22nd and 29th of January 2015 and their corresponding hindcasts have been used to assess the forecast quality (described in the 5.2 section) to predict the first week of February (from 2nd to 8th). To evaluate the forecast quality in the three different prediction systems, we compare the predicted ten-

metre wind speed with the wind speed values from ERA-Interim reanalysis (Dee et al., 2011). The results of the study are shown in Section 6.1.

Although these prediction systems produce predictions of wind speed at 6-hourly or daily frequencies, we have based our analysis on weekly means in order to remove the short term fluctuations and capture the skill from slow changes in the boundary forcings. In the sub-seasonal case, start dates group all the weeks in the same month to provide more robust statistics.

In addition, we will explore the sub-seasonal predictions at global scale employing the forecasts from ECMWF prediction system. Finally, we will apply the same methodology also to assess the skill associated not only to the wind speed but also to the ENSO and the NAO indices, which are sources of predictability of wind speed at this timescale (see Figure 8). We are also planning to explore the main drivers of wind speed at sub-seasonal timescales as well as the differences between the predictability over the land or the ocean.

5.1.2 Seasonal predictions

In this study we use the ten-metre wind speed forecasts from ECMWF System 4 (Molteni et al., 2011), a leading operational seasonal prediction system based on a fully coupled general circulation model. The operational System 4 (S4) forecasts are produced at the beginning of each month with 51-member ensembles. Each member of the ensemble uses slightly different initial conditions and different realizations of stochastic representations of subgrid physical processes in the atmosphere, because ensemble predictions are a way to deal with uncertainties in the climate system, in particular those associated with the imperfections of the initial conditions. The simulations are performed for up to seven months into the future.

To evaluate the S4 prediction quality, we compare the predicted ten-metre wind speed with the ten-metre wind speed from the ERA-Interim reanalysis (Dee et al., 2011). Given the sparsity of global wind observations, we consider the reanalysis as the best available estimate of wind speed.

These datasets have been used to analyze the different predictability of one of the state-of-the-art seasonal prediction systems to predict the wind speeds with different lead times and in different seasons. This analysis has been performed for two key regions in Europe, the North Sea and the Iberian Peninsula. In addition a separate analysis of the predictability considering land-only predictions or those predictions over the sea have been done in order to identify the possible differences between the sources of predictability in the ocean and in continental region.

Two of the main sources of predictability at seasonal timescales are both the NAO and the Niño phenomena (explained in the section 4.3.2.) and in order to illustrate which is the impact of these phenomena on the seasonal wind speed we have performed an analysis based on the seasonal ten-metre wind speeds from the ERA-Interim reanalyses.

The NAO and ENSO are each characterized with standard indices. The principal component (PC) based NAO index defined by Hurrell et al. (2010) is used for the NAO. NAO index data have been obtained from the National Center for Atmospheric Research

(NCAR) (<https://climatedataguide.ucar.edu/climate-data/hurrell-north-atlantic-oscillation-nao-index-pc-based>). The “Oceanic Niño Index” (ONI) has been used to identify El Niño events. Seasonal index values are characterized with ERSSTv4 (centered 30-year base periods) or the 3-month running average in Niño 3.4, with the same selected area. Niño index data have been obtained from the CPC (<http://www.cpc.ncep.noaa.gov/data/indices/>)

Wind data are stratified according to the corresponding values of the two reference indices (NAO Index and ONI). For stratification purposes, a criterion is defined for each reference index, which sorts index values into “positive”, “negative” or “neutral”. The criterion used for the NIÑO 3.4 index is a fixed threshold of plus or minus 0,5°C of temperature anomalies, which is the established criterion for declaring Niño or Niña phases. Values above 0.5°C are considered “positive” (what is called a warm or “Niño” phase); those below -0.5°C are considered “negative” (what is called a cold or “Niña” phase); the values lying between -0.5°C and 0.5°C are considered neutral. As to the NAO index, in the absence of a widespread and established criterion, terciles are used as the thresholds to define the three “positive”, “negative” and “neutral” categories. The temporal mean of each category (positive, negative or neutral) is obtained. Finally, a comparison by subtraction is made between each of three stratified wind groups, in the following two combinations: Positive-Neutral and Negative-Neutral.

The resulting fields are masked, removing ocean grid points with depths greater than 50 m, as a threshold of 50 m depth has been a technical limitation for offshore wind farms in recent years (Arapogianni et al., 2013). However current basements can reach up to 80m, and the recently developed floating turbines have been tested at depths up to 200m, enabling the development of offshore in a much larger extension (Deep water EWEA, 2013). For that reason, further research on a more appropriate mask will be undertaken in the future.

In order to check whether the observed differences are truly attributable to index change, and not to intrinsic variability, a Student's t-test is performed between the two combinations above (Positive-Neutral and Negative-Neutral), for each grid point, with the still unaveraged data, to obtain the significant value of the difference. Significant values at the 95% confidence level are shown with dots.

In the next months we are going to reproduce these analyses for the Météo France seasonal prediction system (Voltaire et al., 2013) in order to get more robust conclusions.

5.1.3 Decadal predictions

Decadal predictions are a field of research that is on early stages, so we lack examples illustrating the methodology. Differently from seasonal and sub-seasonal forecasts, decadal predictions require the construction of an ensemble of decadal prediction models. Such a multi-member, multi-model ensemble is structured in the same way of the multi-models based on climate projections (30-100 years); one of the main differences is that only one emission scenario is usually employed in the decadal predictions (the e1b scenario for the CMIP5 decadal models).

After first tentative, multi-model of 6-hourly wind speed is developed based on the CMIP5 decadal dataset, the skill of each single model is evaluated individually and compared with the skill of the multi-model, for example by means of a Taylor diagram. The worst models (in terms of wind speed correlation and RMSE between models and observations) are then discarded and the remaining models are used to generate the new, improved multi-model.

Once the final multi-model is selected, its predictions are evaluated using the same scores employed at the other timescales, grouping data by month (as for the seasonal predictions).

5.2 Forecast quality assessment

Climate predictions have to be systematically compared to a reference, preferably observations, to assess their overall quality in a multifaceted process known as forecast quality assessment (Doblas-Reyes et al., 2005).

At sub-seasonal to decadal scales, forecasts have to be probabilistic to estimate uncertainties realistically and probabilistic verification of ensemble forecasts serves numerous purposes, including:

- (i) To provide information and guidance regarding benefits and deficiencies associated with changes in the predictions systems, which can feed back into system improvements
- (ii) To evaluate the impact of the components of the prediction system such as land data assimilation, the ability to predict NAO, MJO and other phenomena (e.g. blocking, storm track variations, etc.), and the dependence on ENSO.
- (iii) To provide meaningful information for decision making.

A common set of deterministic and probabilistic metrics is applied for the assessment of wind-speed forecasts for both the sub-seasonal, seasonal and decadal scale. All verification scores are applied to the forecast anomalies rather than the absolute wind speed values, as there is a clear seasonality in wind speed. The goal is to offer the most general and, a priori, relevant information for a user in the wind energy sector instead of the traditional view offered by climate scientist where the information provided to the users is mainly based on correlation.

The skill estimates based on the performance of the system in the past, may guide users about the expected performance of the future forecasts. Both deterministic (ensemble mean) and probabilistic skill scores are considered as measures of the degree of improvement (or worsening) of the different climate prediction systems compared to the climatology.

The first validation score to be considered evaluates the predictions in terms of the temporal correlation coefficient of the anomalies (ACC), on a grid point by grid point basis. ACC is not a recommendable measure to be provided to the users because it is a deterministic measure that only considers the ensemble mean and doesn't include information about the predictions uncertainty. Although there is more value in the forecasts if the full predictive distribution is analyzed and taken into account when an end user is faced with making decisions (Gneiting 2011), the ACC has been used as an indicator of the potential predictability which can be obtained with a good calibration.

A measure of the predictive skill for the probabilistic forecasts for categorical events is the Ranked Probability Skill Score (RPSS) which is a squared distance between the cumulative probabilities of the categorical forecasts and reference climatology (Wilks, 2011) that is the preferred current choice of the wind energy users. The RPSS employed is a recently developed enhanced version of the standard RPSS that not only is a probabilistic and strictly proper skill score, but it also has the advantage of not penalizing the intrinsic unreliability induced by small ensemble sizes, a property that is favorable in the present project, since the ensemble size of different forecasting systems varies greatly, from only a few members to more than 50, and allow to compare prediction systems with a different number of members.

The RPSS has been computed based on categorical forecasts for terciles. We have considered three equi-probable events associated with the two terciles of the climatological distribution of the reference: wind speed exceeding the upper tercile, not exceeding the lower tercile and between the two terciles. This is only one example, other categories could be defined if they represent the decisions involved in precautionary climate action.

Scores below zero indicates that the predictions are unskillful, those equal to zero are equal to the climatology forecasts, and anything above zero is an improvement upon climatology, up to 1, which indicates a 'perfect' forecast.

6. Preliminary results of Initial Predictability Assessment

6.1 Sub-seasonal predictions results

The skill assessment of the 10-metre wind speed from the monthly prediction system from ECMWF is compared with the ERA-Interim reanalysis, which has been used as reference, shown in Figure 9. The hindcasts of five weekly start dates of January 2014, which correspond to the 2nd, 9th, 16th, 23th and 30th of January, have been concatenated in order to estimate the skill scores for that particular month. The hindcast period is 20 years long (1994-2013), thus each skill score was applied to a set of 100 observations-forecasts pairs. Globally, there is a positive skill that indicates that the ECMWF monthly prediction system has predictability for the 12 to 18 days forecast time. In Europe, the strongest skill scores occur across areas of the North Atlantic, United Kingdom and Scandinavia, mainly due to larger SST gradients, stronger coupling between the stratosphere and the troposphere, and influence from the MJO (Lynch et al., 2014).

The two scores show a similar spatial distribution, even if some differences in the level of skill can be observed. These differences indicate that although the potential predictability of the monthly prediction systems is high, the prediction of the terciles of the wind speed is still a challenge in some regions. The dominant positive values of the scores indicate that the ECMWF monthly prediction system produces useful information that could be included in the decision making processes related with the wind energy operations.

Figure 9. Comparison of two skill scores for 10-m wind speed for the hindcasts of January 1994-2013: ACC (left) and Fair RPSS (right). A forecast time of 12-18 days is considered. A skill score of 1 indicates a perfect forecast; 0 is equal to climatology, and therefore anything better than 0 is an improvement on climatology.

Figure 10. Correlation coefficient of 10-m wind speed for the hindcasts of January 1995-2014. The forecast time of 19-25 (top) 12-18 (middle) and 5-11 (bottom) days are considered. A correlation of 1 indicates a perfect forecast; 0 is equal to climatology, and therefore anything better than 0 is an improvement on climatology. Locations where the correlation is significant at the 95% confidence level are marked with dots.

In the analysis for European region the Figure 9 illustrates the predictability at sub-seasonal timescales. The positive values of the correlation in Europe indicate that there is potential skill in this region, and the wind speeds could be predicted almost 3 weeks

in advance when the CMA and ECMWF models show significant skill in regions as the North Sea, Denmark or Germany. The three prediction systems display some differences, as can be observed for the forecast time of 19-25 days when the NCEP system shows positive and significant values in central Europe while the CMA and ECMWF prediction systems have stronger values in Northern Europe. However the results indicate that there is consistent performance of the three systems with predominant positive in the European region.

The three considered prediction systems also displays negative correlation values in Europe. This is a well-known problem that has been attributed to the influence of atmospheric circulation changes, local orography and the latent heat fluxes over the warmer sea surface.

Figure 11. Ranked probability skill scores for terciles of 10-m wind speed for the hindcasts of January 1995-2014. The forecast time of 19-25 (top) 12-18 (middle) and 5-11 (bottom) days are considered. A correlation of 1 indicates a perfect forecast; 0 is equal to climatology, and therefore anything better than 0 is an improvement on climatology. Locations where the correlation is significant at the 95% confidence level are marked with dots.

The RPSS maps (Figure 11) show similar results to those for the correlation. This skill score is a probabilistic metric that evaluates if the sub-seasonal prediction system is

able to predict tercile categories. Figure 2 shows that some key regions for the wind energy sector as the North Sea, United Kingdom or Germany.

The improvement of the skill is noticeable for both correlation (Figure 10) and RPSS (Figure 11) when the forecast time is shorter, as one would expect, however the positive scores in the forecast times from 12-18 and the 19-25 days is an encouraging result. It evidences the existing predictability of the sub-seasonal prediction systems of the wind speeds in Europe, and the potential usability of the predictions of wind speed at this timescale for the wind energy industry.

6.2 Seasonal predictions results

6.2.1 Evaluation of the predictability of wind speed at seasonal timescales

A first evaluation of the results from the skill assessment of the ECMWF System 4 for wind speed at seasonal time scale over Europe is presented here. The aim is to provide an overview of the current wind predictability and identify which is the most useful information for the wind energy community.

ECMWF System 4 provides seasonal predictions up to six months ahead. In this section we analyze the retrospective operational forecasts (hindcasts) of this prediction systems, over the past 32 years, from 1981 to 2013. In this deliverable we have only illustrated the predictability for the boreal winter (December, January and February). This means that the used forecast months are from one to three for the forecasts initialized in December (lead time 0), two to four for those forecasts initialized in November (lead time 1), three to five for the forecasts initialized in October (lead time 2) and four to six for the forecast initialized in September (lead time 3).

Figure 12 shows large areas where System 4 has positive skill for the predictions of winter in the European region. There is a clear difference in the spatial distribution of the skillful areas for the considered lead times. For the lead time 0 (Figure 12 a) the stronger correlation appears over many parts of Europe, although statistically significant points are mainly located across north Europe. For lead time 1, eastern Mediterranean region has skill when forecast is made in November (Figure 12 b), while for lead time 2 and 3 (Figure 12 c and Figure 12 d) the stronger skill is displayed over western Europe (except Iberian Peninsula) and the North Sea. However, there are regions, like Mediterranean basin, that have very poor skill for the four analyzed lead times.

Similar patterns to those showed in the Figure 12 could be observed in Figure 13 for the RPSS although it displays fewer areas with statically significant skill than the areas showed for the correlation. This result is in agreement with the remarks of the previous section (6.1); the prediction of the terciles of the wind speed is still a challenge in some regions.

Figure 12. Anomaly correlation coefficient between 10-m wind speed of the ECMWF System-4 hindcasts and ERA-Interim in the period from 1981 to 2013. Forecasts of the boreal winter (DJF) have been considered at forecast times: a) 1-3 months (Lead time 0), b) 2-4 months (Lead time 1), c) 3-5 months (Lead time 2) and d) 4-6 months (Lead time 3). Locations where the correlation is significant at the 95% confidence level are marked with dots.

Figure 13. Ranked probability skill score (RPSS) for tercile categories of 10-m wind speed from ECMWF System-4 hindcasts and ERA-Interim in the period from 1981 to 2013. Forecasts of the boreal winter (DJF) have been considered at forecast times: a) 1-3 months (Lead time 0), b) 2-4 months (Lead time 1), c) 3-5 months (Lead time 2) and d) 4-6 months (Lead time 3). Locations where the correlation is significant at the 95% confidence level are marked with dots.

In order to illustrate the relationship between the lead times and of the skill, Figure 14 shows the time evolution of correlation skill for two points. The two selected points are the Alai experimental park and Fino met mast, which are two typical key points for the wind energy community.

Figure 14. Evolution of the Anomaly Correlation Coefficient between 10-m wind speed of ECMWF System4 hindcasts and ERA-Interim with different initialization months (x-axis) in the period from 1981 to 2013 for the prediction of the boreal winter. Two particular points have been selected: Alai experimental Find Farm (top) and Fino (bottom) locations.

To sum up, ECMWF System4 has relevant skill in some areas of Europe, where end users could take advantage of the seasonal forecasts. These predictions can provide information about how likely is that the coming season could be more or less windy than normal, which could help, to improve the planning and to save money in the operations and maintenance of wind farms.

The key to improve the decisions seems to be related with the location of the area of interest, that it is the location of a particular wind farm. The seasonal forecast can provide additional “value” or not to the decisions depending on whether the location is or is not in a skillful. The choice of the most useful prediction at an appropriate lead time is the second critical factor, since the spatial pattern changes with the lead time. However a further analysis based on the sources of skill that drive the wind speed predictability at the particular lead times considered should be performed to gather more robust conclusions.

6.2.2 Characterization of the mechanisms driving wind speed

The NAO and the ENSO are well known climatic phenomena, both with a sizable impact on climate dynamics. To assess the mechanisms driving seasonal wind-speed variability over Europe, we have performed an evaluation of the impact of the North Atlantic Oscillation (NAO) (Figure 14) and the El Niño Southern Oscillation (ENSO) phenomenon (Figure 15) on wind. This evaluation has been performed for each individual season (DJF, MAM, JJA and SON) over the period 1981-2014 with ERA-Interim reanalysis. From each of the NAO and Niño3.4 indices, the years inside three equiprobable categories have been identified and the wind-speed maps been obtained.

A positive phase of the North Atlantic Oscillation has a marked effect upon wind speed in the north of Europe, and Northern Africa. Wind speed increases in these regions during positive phases. In the Iberian Peninsula and the Mediterranean region the effect is the opposite: a positive NAO phase causes a decrease in wind speeds. When the NAO shifts from positive to negative, the effects are reversed. Northern Europe and Northern Africa experience decreased wind speed, and Spain and the Mediterranean region experience an increase in wind speed. The transition zones between areas with positive and negative correlation show a rather neutral effect. These zones are the transition between Northern and Southern Europe, and the transition between the Mediterranean coast of Africa and the Sahara region.

The North Atlantic Oscillation (Figure 14) is a great source of skill for wind speed seasonal predictions in Europe, and to a much lesser extent in East and Central Asia.

Figure 14. Difference in wind speed (m/s) between years with a positive NAO index and years with a neutral NAO (top) and between years with a negative NAO index and years with a neutral NAO for DJF. Locations where the difference is significant at the 95% confidence level are marked with dots.

A positive phase of the El Niño (Figure 15, top) causes increases in wind speed in northern South America. The effects of El Niño are centered around coastal regions. Further north, a positive phase is associated with lower wind speeds in the Caribbean sea and the central United States, as well as in Indonesia. The Pacific Islands lying in the tropics also experience an increase in wind speed. Europe barely experiences any effects.

A negative phase (Figure 15, bottom) of the El Niño has a less pronounced effect upon wind speed. Slight increases are produced in the US and the Caribbean. The effects in South America are less prominent, being most of them variations of small magnitude, although of high statistical significance. Oceanic countries experience the most intense variations in a somewhat reversed pattern as what is seen during a positive phase. The southern half of Indonesia experiences an increase, and the upper half a decrease, both statistically significant. Moderate but statistically significant effects are perceived in Central Europe, where wind speeds experience slight decreases.

The Niño displays only moderate usefulness in wind speed predictions in North America, South America and Southeast Asia. However, the Niño is of a marked oceanic nature, and may serve as a strong tool for wind farm management.

Figure 15. Difference in wind speed (m/s) between years with a positive ONI index and years with a neutral ONI (top) and between years with a negative ONI index and years with a neutral ONI for DJF. Locations where the difference is significant at the 95% confidence level are marked with dots.

7. Conclusions and Outlook

This deliverable provides an exhaustive description of the predictability of the forecast systems to simulate the wind speed, from short-term forecasts to decadal predictions, thorough sub-seasonal and seasonal forecasts. It also includes a comprehensive view of their potential applications, sources of predictability, available prediction systems and verification methodology.

For each time scale, the wind speed forecasts are firstly assessed comparing them with observations from a reanalysis employing one deterministic verification score and one probabilistic score, respectively the correlation coefficient of the anomalies (ACC) and the ranked probability skill score (RPSS).

Then, for each time scale the relationships between wind speed and its main climate drivers (Figure 8) are evaluated, to assess the strength of the influence of each source of predictability on wind speed.

Preliminary results from the hindcast analysis detected at least two windows of opportunity (high forecast skill) over Europe, one at sub-seasonal time scale, for a lead time of 12-18 days, and another at seasonal scale, for a lead time of one month. This skill is found to exist mainly over Central and Northern Europe and to a lesser degree in the Iberian Peninsula during the winter months of December-February.

Having demonstrated that there is statistically significant wind speed skill during winter over some European areas, the end users could gain potential economic value using the forecasts instead of the climatology to base their decisions. Over these areas, novel techniques that employ this probabilistic information effectively to enhance the value of operational business decisions and quantitative risk management in the wind energy sector can be developed.

In case of station data availability, it will be possible to explore and assess also such local data at all time scales using the same methodology described in the deliverable for the reanalysis data.

One of the main objectives of this task is to help decision maker to answer the question: what can they expect on the use of wind forecast at different time horizons? How predictable the wind resource is at the site of interest?

At the end of the project our aim is to provide a clear description of the predictability of climate predictions at different time scales assessing the evolution of this predictability in different European regions. Rather than coming up with complex estimates of different characteristics of forecast skill and reliability whose relevance strongly depends on the specific application the preliminary results illustrated, in this deliverable we are going to be included in an easy interpretive and user-friendly example for an end user. This could be a similar tool to the information developed by Weisheimer and Palmer (2014) for precipitation and temperature seasonal forecasts (Figure 16), but for near-surface wind speed at sub-seasonal to decadal timescales and focusing in different European regions.

Figure 16 shows in a simple way the predictability of the seasonal forecasts in different seasons by categorizing the regions depending on whether the prediction is reliable or not. This summarized and tailored information about the predictability could be easily integrated in the European Wind Atlas, allowing the application of the predictions at sub-seasonal to decadal timescales in a decision-making context.

In case of station data availability, it would also be possible to explore and assess the local data at different time horizons based on the methodology described on this deliverable for the reanalysis data. In this sense, it would be interesting to use the wind data base developed in the task 2.6 which is performed in the NEWA project. Measures of long term wind data could provide a more independent validation exercise than the validation based only on ERA interim near-surface wind data. Besides the fact of using different databases for validation could provide end-users with a more reliable knowledge of the useful information from the day-ahead to multi-decadal time scale forecasts.

Figure 16. Reliability of System 4 seasonal forecasts for 2 m temperature. (a) Cold DJF, (b) warm DJF, (c) cold JJA and (d) warm JJA. Source; Weisheimer and Palmer (2014).

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Annex: Supplementary information

Figure A1. Same as Figure 15 but for the March-April-May season.

Figure A2. Same as Figure 15 but for the June-July-August season.

Figure A3. Same as Figure 15 but for the September-October-November season.

Figure A4. Same as Figure 14 but for the March-April-May season.

Figure A5. Same as Figure 14 but for the June-July-August season.

Figure A6. Same as Figure 14 but for the September-October-November season.

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